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UPWARDS

Deliverable D8.3

Progress reports on exploitation activities

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Task	8.4	Exploitation of the project results

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

³ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

Deliverable abstract

The scope of this deliverable is to present current exploitation plan of the UPWARDS project's results.

This deliverable is related to the task 8.4 "Exploitation of the project results" and gives an overview of current strategy for exploitation of the project's results.

The report is written by Wavestone in collaboration with SAMTECH.

The report will be further updated in M36 and M48.

Deliverable Review

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(ii) That needs improvement of the writing by the originator of the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(iii) That needs further work by the Partners responsible for the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a

* Type of comments: M = Major comment; m = minor comment; a = advice

Table of content

1. Introduction	4
2. UPWARDS project outline	5
3. Market analysis	6
3.1. Identification of the project stakeholders and interested audience.....	6
3.2. Current market study for wind turbines	9
4. Updated exploitation strategy per partner	12
5. Knowledge management and intellectual property	18
5.1. Data management plan	18
5.2. IP management strategy	18
6. Standardization, policy-making and regulations	19
6.1. Identification of applicable standards	19
7. Conclusions	20

1. Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is to comply with the task 8.4 “Exploitation of the project results” and to give a plan of possible exploitation strategies of the project results.

The report contains a current analysis of major elements and findings related to the future valorisation of the project results. It gives potential strategies for commercialisation and standardisation via action plans, including building a strong network of potential customers, defining the project market and possible business cases.

Current report is the first version of the exploitation strategy plan at Month 24. The report will be updated as the project progresses: two main updates will be delivered at Month 36 (second version) and at Month 48 (final version).

2. UPWARDS project outline

In OECD countries, gross electricity production from renewable products reached 2,731.8TWh in 2017; 5.1 % higher than 2016. This represents around 25% of the total electricity production. The growth rate of electricity generation from renewable energy sources has been growing at an average rate of 2.7% per year; almost double the rate for the total electricity production (1.3%).

Figure 1: Renewables shares in OECD electricity production in 2017 (IEA report 2018).

In this context, UPWARDS project aims in development of virtual prototype (through High Fidelity numerical simulations) of larger and more efficient wind turbines in order to increase sustainable and renewable electricity in Europe and worldwide. Current wind farms have reached their maximum size and cannot be optimized without better understanding of related physical phenomena. Indeed, the increase in size of wind turbine is needed in order to accelerate the development and deployment of cost-effective low carbon technologies. As the electricity generated by wind farms is the results of complexes physical phenomena between wind, rotor, drive train and generator, UPWARDS project aims in deep understanding of those interactions. To face this challenge, UPWARDS develops HPC framework for integrated high-fidelity dynamic simulations of the interaction between wind, the wind turbine structural mechanical system (composite blades, rotor, drivetrain, bedplate, tower, fixed or floating foundation) and the smart machine control devices. The HPC simulation framework represents next generation dynamic multi-physics and mechatronic simulation technology.

With further development after UPWARDS, this HPC framework will pave the way for extensive virtual prototyping of wind turbines, that will speed up wind turbine development and reduce the need for prototype testing. Several aspects of wind turbine technology can be exploited with high fidelity simulation.

3. Market analysis

This section contains a list of identified project stakeholders and interested audiences, as well as an updated market study for wind turbines at M24.

3.1. Identification of the project stakeholders and interested audience.

Prior to define an actual exploitation strategy, it is required to identify stakeholders and potential audiences. In the case of UPWARDS project, by stakeholders we understand individuals that are impacted by the project achievements and the audience are the message receivers. The stakeholders can give a feedback and may influence decision-makers in the scope of the project development. Specially conceived communication and dissemination messages, channels and tools are used by UPWARDS partners in order to reach both stakeholders and interested audience.

A specific deliverable is dedicated to this section: **D8.4 “Stakeholder engagement”**. Major findings of this deliverable related to the stakeholder’s analysis and activities in this domain, written by Wageningen University in collaboration with Wavestone, are summarized in the Table 1 below.

A specific stakeholder with whom a partnership would enable many interesting synergies, is the IOTwins consortium (another H2020 funded project). The IOTwins project is focused on the lowering of Barriers-to-entry (BTEs) for companies across several industries in implementing internet-of-things (hardware & software) infrastructure to enable the next generation of industry in Europe. This is aimed to be done through technical development of the next generation of platform solutions by means of several test-beds. This project overlaps with the interests of UPWARDS as 1 of the test-beds that will be developed is focused on the predictive maintenance and maintenance plan optimization of wind turbines. This work would provide a useful complement to the various simulation packages being developed by the UPWARDS project for the design, development, production & testing of the next generation of wind turbines.

For UPWARDS, the following types of audience/stakeholder have been identified:

Table 1: Stakeholders and main audience

Stakeholders within the UPWARDS consortium	
UPWARDS consortium partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wageningen University and Research, The Netherlands • Aalborg University, Denmark • AWA Truepower SL, Spain • The Fraunhofer Society, Germany • Samtech SA, Belgium • Sintef AS, Norway • Siemens Gamesa renewable Energy AS, Denmark • Siemens industry software NV, Belgium • National University of the Littoral, Argentina • Wavestone, Luxemburg • Von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics, Belgium

External stakeholders (within EU)	
Associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WindEurope, Belgium, Brussels • European Renewable Energies Federation, Belgium, Brussels • European Council for Energy Efficient Economy, Sweden, Stockholm • European Energy Research Alliance, Belgium, Brussels • European Technology and Innovation Platform on wind energy, Belgium, Brussels • European Forum for Renewable Energy Sources (EUFORES), Belgium, Brussels • European Renewable Energy Centres Agency, Belgium, Brussels • European Association for Renewable Energies (EUROSOLAR), Germany, Bonn • REScoop, Belgium, Berchem
Private sector engagement	<p>Manufacturer of wind turbines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Siemens Gamesa renewable Energy, Spain <p>Wind energy developers and energy company:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PowerPeers, Netherlands • Samenom, Netherlands • Van der bron, Netherlands • PureEnergie, Enschede, the Netherlands <p>Test site:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test center Osterlid of DTU wind energy, Denmark <p>Government initiative by to support energy transition in the NL:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Millieucentrale, Netherlands
Other stakeholders	<p>European platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETIPWind • ETIP SNET • ZEP • ETP4HPC • EERA
Members of advisory board (External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB))	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eugene de Beer, The Netherlands, Peutz • Ivan Pineda, Belgium, Wind Europe • Gudmund Olsen, Norway, Statoil • Todd Griffith, USA, Sandia Nat. Lab. • Amilcar Quispitupa, Denmark, DNV-GL

External stakeholders	
Global networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Energy Agency, Paris, France • IRENA International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, Dubai • Renewables Now • 100% renewables, Germany, Bonn • American Wind Energy Association, USA, Washington, DC • Centre for Sustainable Energy (CSE), UK, Bristol • Energy 21, Utrecht, the Netherlands • Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC), Brussels, Belgium • World Renewable Energy Congress, UK • World Council for Renewable Energy, Bonn, Germany • WINDEXchange, USA • US Department of Energy, USA • The Wind Energy Institute of Canada (WEICan), Canada
Community stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Danish association of wind turbine owners, Danmarks Vindmølleforening (DV) • WindCentrale • Energy Academy • Public/ local communities

3.2. Current market study for wind turbines

As per European Commission reports, Europe will require around 450 GW of offshore wind by 2050 which will be 30% of Europe's electricity demand in 2050. However, several economic, technical, social and environmental aspects inhibit the development of wind parks to meet these targets. One of the challenges is the design and optimization of large wind turbines, in terms of material use and reliability.

Moreover, moving towards renewable energy sources is the only way to reach a climate neutral power supply. This is necessary to achieve the goals defined in the Paris agreement to address climate change. Wind energy offers the lowest levelized cost of energy and therefore will play a major role in the transition of the energy supply system.

The wind industry is a booming market with a significant annual growth. It is also an industry in full transformation with some clear trends:

- Shift towards large offshore wind parks.
- High pressure on the costs of wind farms (CAPEX & OPEX).
- A consolidation amongst the turbine OEMs and suppliers is going on.
- Driven by higher margins, OEMs are diverting towards new service models, where also assets of the competition are envisaged.

It is clear, that in today's technology driven market, the biggest challenge companies active in the wind industry are facing, is how to effectively handle all these transitions. Digital transformation is key to mastering these challenges and unleashing innovation.

As per information available on the CORDIS portal, current EU-funded projects on wind energy are focusing on:

Project	Technology focus
PROMOTION	Network infrastructure to link off-shore wind parks and on-shore grids via HVDC technology (Diode Rectifier offshore converter, an HVDC grid protection system using multi-vendor approach, and HVDC circuit breaker prototypes), covering medium to high TRL.
WinWind	Analysis of social acceptance of wind energy regarding regional and local communities' specificities, socioeconomic, spatial & environmental characteristics and the reasons for slow market deployment in the target regions.
WInspector	Investigation for defect presence on a wind turbine blade by using specially designed platforms that can reach the blade and implement faster inspections on site. Commercialization of WInspector, an agile robotic platform able to climb up the wind turbine tower and deploy an advanced Digital Shearography kit that carries out the inspection of a blade at a depth of up to 50mm.
REACH	Airborne wind energy system, that allow supplying remote communities and off-grid areas with reliable and clean electricity in a cost-competitive way.
ZephyCloud-2	Software tools for wind modelling and a cloud-based simulation platform.
ELICAN	Integrated substructure system for deep offshore wind energy, which consists in designing, building, certifying and fully demonstrating in operative environment a deep-water substructure prototype supporting Adwen's 5MW offshore wind turbine.
ROMEO	Development and demonstration of an Operation & Maintenance information management and analytics platform capable of improving the decision-making processes of offshore wind farms' operators allowing the transition from calendar base maintenance to condition-based maintenance strategies.
Riblet4Wind	Demonstrating the transfer of the riblet-coating technology from the aeronautics sector to the wind energy industry, in order to increase the efficiency of wind turbines.

The EU seeks to improve European competitiveness on wind energy as outlined in the European Strategic Energy Technology Plan, which is focused on developing large-scale turbines in the range 10-20 MW, to reach 450 GW as part of the Commission scenario to deliver climate neutrality by 2050.

The larger wind turbines are much more beneficial compared to the smaller wind turbines as they produce more energy more efficiently. In the last 2-3 decades the rated effect of wind turbines have risen from the kW range to the MW range. The largest turbine sizes in operation are:

- GE Haliade-X 12 MW wind turbine,
- Siemens Gamesa 10 MW wind turbine SG 10.0-193 DD upgraded to SG 11.0-193 DD Flex,
- Vestas V164 with a rated capacity of 8 MW and later upgraded to 5 MW.

The natural next iteration is to design a 15 MW wind turbine. **Therefore, one of the objectives in the UPWARDS project is to develop a 15MW virtual wind turbine.** This has been designed by Siemens Gamesa (one of the project partners) together with SINTEF (the project coordinator). Furthermore, the wind turbine specifications will soon be publicly available.

Although UPWARDS' developments potentially have other sectors of application (e.g. aeronautics, aviation, automotive, to name some), the project's roadmap will focus on the wind energy sector, as the stage of development (TRL 4) is too early to be more specific.

Figure 2: Major trends in the wind industry.

There is clear shift towards offshore wind parks. The logistics and investments are heavier, but the availability of constant high wind is much greater than on land.

There is high pressure on the costs of wind farms since at the latest auctions, the offshore wind farms are granted without any subsidy. The ROI must be guaranteed by low CAPEX and OPEX. This automatically leads to large wind farms (up to 4GW at Hornsea, UK) equipped with large wind turbines (6MW is now the standard for offshore – GamesaSiemens Direct-drive, 8 MW Vestas V-164).

Consolidation is taking place. The 4 biggest wind turbine makers (Vestas, GamesaSiemens, Goldwind and GE) had in 2017 a market-share of 54%. The competition is increasing, and the aim is by advanced designs (e.g. direct drive turbines, more efficient blades, etc.) but also by clever fleet management (e.g. optimized maintenance schedules or simply less maintenance by increased reliability of the installations) to attract more business.

In brief, the European market for renewables, though facing barriers, shows a growing trend so UPWARDS' consortium can develop their exploitation strategy in the medium-term.

In the long-term, UPWARDS integrated simulation framework will be introduced in the global market around the world that, as can be seen is currently led by China, USA, Germany and India. Globally, there is a worldwide growing trend in wind investments that UPWARDS will take advantage of once the developments are ready for commercialization.

SWOT analysis

The following SWOT analysis was updated on M24 of UPWARDS project.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The new simulation environment brings CAPEX/OPEX advantages, environmental and administrative benefits, thus able to attract investors. • Environmental advantages (i.e. less noise, less visual impact and a less impact on wildlife), are to improve wind communities' and regional authorities' perception on wind technologies • Stringent need of green electricity production. • Less development time for new technologies can increase the amount of R&D projects on wind energy and improve their time-to-market roadmap (such as new off-shore and VAWT designs). • International network of stakeholders boosts global exploitation of the project's findings and results in the medium-, long-term (2025-2030). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wind energy is utterly variable and brings changes in operation that have to be balanced (increasing its price). • Grid network's upgrades are necessary if more wind projects are to be implemented. • Currently, in private companies HPC approaches are demanding in time and costly, making their application to the wind energy sector not-cost effective at the moment. • Wind energy farms have an inherent impact in neighbor communities. Permit and EIA for implementation are necessary and long to achieve.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European low-carbon transition is a priority reflected in policies and regulation, at the EU and MS level. • HPC approaches receive strong support from the EU, as there are numerous sets of big data not being used for key applications. • Existing trend to have larger WT (as opposite to smaller units). Increasing costs of testing favor digital approaches. • Need to reduce the Levelized Cost Of Electricity (LCOE): WT manufacturers have to increase their R&D spending. The industry's efforts to reduce the LCOE and manufacturers' attempts to avoid the compression of sales margins for new products. • Digitalization to increase energy harvesting efficiency and lower OPEX. • There are ambitions plans to increase investments in wind energy capacity installations (NAP and EU targets). This is an opportunity for WT manufacturers and thus UPWARDS consortium (more demand is benefited by decreased prototype testing time). • Global trend to increase wind installations (North America, Latin America and MEA). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower prices brought by Chinese WT manufacturers affect EU competitiveness (400-500 k€/MW vs 1 Mio €/MW) • Heterogeneous regulation per MS causes less access to financing to wind innovative technologies • Regulations are based on various criteria, but not on pollution generation. There is thus no clear scheme supporting wind technologies; • There is no direct EU regulation in noise • The Emission Trade System favors large companies mainly and does not provide reasons for investors to address renewable energy technologies other than GHG abatement • If HPC approaches are to be implemented, existing CPUs have to be improved to shorten computational times at a competitive cost • Land ownership issues are not being addressed • There is an administrative burden to wind project implementation (i.e. too many authorities to be contacted to obtain permits and certifications)

4. Updated exploitation strategy per partner

UPWARDS aims at improving the understanding of wind turbine related physical phenomena. This includes the full digitalization of wind turbine development, allowing to design and test them in a 15 MW virtual prototype during the project.

UPWARDS faces the challenge to optimize the design of future wind turbines according to technical, economic and societal demands. Such endeavor needs to be backed up by a robust exploitation strategy and a realistic roadmap agreed by the consortium. The common vision of the partnership is to develop knowledge and innovative models that can be introduced in a commercial simulation platform, and also be the basis of future consulting and training services for WT developers, wind farm owners and operators. Such models can be also exploited individually in commercial, academic and in further research initiatives.

The exploitation strategies, set up in the beginning of the project, were updated by several partners at M24 and are outlined in the following table.

Table 2: Exploitation strategy per partner at M24.

Technology / know-how	Partners involved	Exploitation strategy
UPWARDS high fidelity integrated simulation framework	All	<p>Samtech and Siemens (SWP and SISW) are the industrial partners in charge of developing the WT model software and WT virtual prototyping. ITWM will create an OpenInterface in which UPWARDS' models will be integrated. The rest of the partners (academia, RTOs, private companies) are in charge of developing mathematical models that will be integrated in such environment, addressing fluid dynamics, acoustics, composite failure and socioeconomics.</p> <p>The main aim of the industrial partners in the long-term is to introduce in the market a simulation framework that allows to carry out design and virtual testing of WT, going from the approximate models available today to having available a full virtual WT twin, in line with the Industry 4.0 concept. The framework will be complimented by training of wind farm owners, operators and wind industry service providers.</p> <p>In order to reach the capability to couple all the technical features already described and bring a robust digital environment to the market, the consortium foresees the development of a <i>roadmap</i> from 2018 (initial date of the project) to 2030 (tools have already been marketed and/or are being the subject of further research projects).</p> <p>From the industrial point of view, Samtech and Siemens (SWP and SISW) aim at being key players in the digital simulation of WT. From the academic/RTO's and commercial point of view, the main objective is to develop their research concepts and bring them to further stages in which they can be used for consulting, future projects and academic purposes. Both visions are complimentary and shape up the partnership presented in UPWARDS.</p>
Park models	SINTEF	<p>Park models for better predictions of wake and turbulence will be developed by SINTEF. Apart from being part of the above mentioned platform, SINTEF, as a RTO will use the project developments to further research and network with the key stakeholders in wind energy. SINTEF as an independent research organization applies for both national and international projects. Competence from UPWARDS will improve the chances for projects.</p>

<p>Socio-economic impact assessment tools and know-how</p>	<p>WUR</p>	<p>WUR will provide knowledge about innovative methods of public and other stakeholder engagement with wind energy, including methods for public engagement in wind turbine design, its implementation and landscape and in long-term management of wind energy infrastructure, up until decommissioning. Looking at all these stages of public and other stakeholder engagement, WUR insights can be used to improve design and certification mechanisms of wind turbines towards more inclusive for different stakeholders. Next to that, insights about public engagement at the stage of planning can be used to improve current practices of spatial planning and local stakeholder engagement to better facilitate citizen led projects, community projects and local planning for renewable energy. Finally, WUR will also generate new insights about what it means for the different stakeholders to be engaged in long-term management and decommissioning of wind turbines and long- management of wind energy landscapes which provides insights for policy makers for governance of energy landscapes.</p> <p>They will use the tools and knowledge developed in an open innovation frame, to participate in research projects and introduce these aspects in research initiatives from early stages.</p>
<p>Computational fluid dynamics/ acoustic models</p>	<p>SISW</p>	<p>SISW will develop software for the UPWARDS simulation framework and their developments might be exploited within Siemens' platforms. In the long-term, their results could be transferred to other sectors such as aviation. With regards to networking, SISW plans to strengthen links with the other partners under Siemens' umbrella (Samtech and SWP). They also have long-lasting collaborations with IVKDF that will be further pursued.</p> <p>Figure 3: Simcenter 3D Acoustics: Dominant noise radiation by blades or tower?</p> <p>The <i>structure borne transfer paths</i> are much more important and in principle there are 2 main energy flows. In both cases, the gearbox is considered as a vibration source and the mechanical energy can be guided towards the non-rotating part of the turbine through the gearbox mounting system. Finally, the energy reaches the tower panels and/or the nacelle walls and these act as a loudspeaker and radiate the noise. At the contrary, a part of the mechanical energy is directed through the rotating interfaces of the gearbox to the outside. In particular the low speed shaft (LSS) plays an important role. The gear meshing energy is then transferred by the LSS towards the hub and the 3 blades. This generates vibration at the blades and these then radiate the noise. In reality, this simple mechanism is more complicated since the LSS is usually supported by a main bearing, which is connected to the same frame on which the gearbox is</p>

		<p>mounted, and the mechanical energy in the rotating shaft will be partially branched towards the main frame and further guided towards e.g. the tower walls where eventually the noise can be generated.</p> <p>Once the dominant transfer paths are identified, this enables further development of countermeasures to reduce the far field exterior noise by focusing only at the critical transfer path and the corresponding noise radiators.</p> <p>Simcenter portfolio offers experimental and numerical tools to reduce and manage noise level produced by wind turbines. Simcenter 3D Acoustics helps minimizing the noise in design variants by simulating exterior acoustic radiation. The entire <i>Source-Transfer-Mechanism</i> is taken into account. The first part describes the excitation, often the gearbox but also the generator in the case of direct drive machines. The energy flow through the entire turbine is quantified and as an output the velocity distribution at the outer panels of the turbine (tower, blades and nacelle walls) is obtained. The air around the turbine is described by FEM or BEM and this medium is loaded by the velocity distribution of the enclosed turbine panels. Finally, the noise is evaluated in e.g. the IEC-61400-11 reference points behind the turbine.</p>
<p>Wind turbine FEA models</p>	<p>Samtech</p>	<p>Samtech will develop the WT model software and they have a central position in the project. Main features to be introduced comprise the flow through the WT, acoustic features and load and material failure prediction models. For the HPC part they have a long-lasting collaboration with Fraunhofer (ITWM). They will exploit the models developed within Siemens' platforms.</p> <div data-bbox="539 1220 1396 1556"> <p>Blades - rotor</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelled by dynamic superelement technique or as beam / shell • Strong aerodynamic coupling (BEM) <p>Rotor shaft</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelled with beam elements <p>Disk brake and slip clutch</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelled using dry friction elements <p>Bedplate-main frame</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelled using dynamic superelement technique <p>Generator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelled by torque / speed law (disconnection and "crow bar" included) <p>Gearbox</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bearings modelled by non-linear bushing elements. • Gears modelled by flexible non-linear gear element. • Shafts modelled by beams </div> <p><i>Figure 4: Simcenter Samcef modelling approaches for different wind turbine components</i></p> <p>Samtech and Siemens Industry Software offer different generic tools like Simcenter 3D Engineering Desktop and Finite Element solvers like Simcenter Nastran (for linear FE analysis) and Simcenter Samcef (for linear and nonlinear FR analysis).</p>

Figure 5: Simcenter Samcef simcenter Nastran, Simcente Samcef

Simcenter Nastran is a standard in the aerospace industry since more than 40 years. It includes now some structural nonlinear capabilities from Samcef (SOL 402).

Simcenter Samcef remains the reference for full nonlinear structural and mechanical analyses capabilities.

The main objective is that Simcenter 3D technology (Simcenter Nastran SOL 402 and Simcenter Samcef) is not limited to metallic components and also includes the possibility of simulating composite components such as wind turbine blades.

The analysis of composites in Simcenter 3D would include the best class solvers for speed and precision to calculate the results of laminated composite structures. Simcenter Samcef will be able to analyze various performance attributes of composite structures, such as structural analysis (linear and non-linear), thermomechanical simulation and acoustics. Moreover, stemming from a decades-long relationship with industries that use composite materials on a large scale, Simcenter Samcef will integrate the ability to accurately model different damage modes. Furthermore, curing thermoset composite parts remains a difficult task as it can lead to the development of residual stresses in the manufactured part, resulting in poor performance, early damage and distortion. Simcenter 3D has the ability to simulate composite manufacturing phenomena such as hardening and crystallization, which will allow to take into account the effects of elastic return and residual stresses.

The central piece of technology is the nonlinear Finite Element solver, Simcenter Samcef Mecano, which some capacities are also available in the Simcenter Nastran SOL402 solution.

Figure 6: Simcenter Samcef Wind Turbine: Fully integrated model of a complete turbine

		<p>Based upon on the Simcenter Samcef Mecano solver, the Siemens goal is to develop a vertical application with the purpose to reproduce the physics of the Wind Turbine submitted to a Wind Field, reacting to different controllers, and being composed of many components, would it be a direct drive system or a gearbox-based design.</p> <p>Simcenter Samcef Mecano is a unique Finite Element solver also capable to model Multi-Body situation thanks to an extensive library of specialized kinematic joints, rigid or flexible. It is the perfect technology to model the rotating shaft, as well as every details of a gearbox inside the machine, including rotating shafts and so on. But when traditional MBS technology mainly uses superelements to represent the flexibility of some of the components, Simcenter Samcef Mecano offers either the capability to use nonlinear beam elements. The tower is an example of this, as well as the different shafts in the gearbox.</p> <p>Moreover, the necessity to apply a proper wind field imposes to keep the rotor blade discretized and not condensed in a superelement so to be capable to apply pressure all over its surface. With Simcenter Samcef Mecano, it is possible to make it geometrically nonlinear so to take into account not only large rotations, but also large deflections e.g. rotor blades may exhibit some bending reaching several meters at the tip of the blade!</p> <p>The heart of the system is the way Simcenter Samcef allows to couple physical phenomena. A typical example is the interaction between the wind and the rotating blades. In Simcenter Samcef Wind Turbine, the wind field is applied to the blade thanks to a BEM formulation. Those equations are solved by Simcenter Samcef Mecano solver in a fully coupled way. The consequence is that the blade “feels” the pressure of the wind, and the wind “sees” the deformed geometry of the blade at every time step.</p> <p>Phenomena like pitch control, pitch errors and yawing can also be perfectly modeled. A vital aspect of the physics is how the behavior of the machine is influenced by different controllers. A Wind Turbine continuously adapts itself to the variations of the Wind. So does a Samcef model! It takes into account the equations of control modeled thanks to Simcenter Amesim, and as a consequence, the way the controllers act on the behavior of the machine. Matlab Simulink format is also compatible with the Simcenter solvers.</p> <p>Similarly, other parts of the Wind Turbine “system” like hydraulics, electricals etc can be modeled with Simcenter Amesim and those models can be linked to the global Wind Turbine model in Samcef Wind Turbine.</p> <p>A specific advantage of Samcef Wind Turbine is the library of parametric models allowing to directly build up to 80 % of a Wind Turbine, from scratch. This leads to important time savings for model preparation. Load case generation is another important aspect, especially in the context of certification when hundreds of standard load cases have to be generated (meaning hundreds of wind fields). Again, Samcef Wind Turbine offers specific capability in this context.</p> <p>Another aspect leading to time saving is the exploitation of Finite Element results to evaluate dynamic behavior of the machine.</p> <p>Again, pre-defined workflow and post-processing allows time saving and full efficiency in this domain.</p>
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<p>Multi-physics numerical methods</p>	<p>UNL</p>	<p>UNL will develop specific models for fluid-structure interaction in WT, in the context of the mechanisms solver from Samtech and the fluid mechanics solver Simcenter STAR-CCM+ from Siemens. The UNL experience in fluid/structure interaction, and also in the particularities of the mechanisms solver and in High Performance Computing, will be used to determine appropriate coupling schemes. Results from this applied research will be used for new research and industrial project developments in the future.</p> <p><i>Figure 7: Simcenter STAR-CCM+ for the simulation of the wake effect behind wind turbines</i></p> <p>To accurately predict real-world performance of wind turbines simulation tools are required that capture the physics that will influence its performance during its operational life, including those that cross the boundaries of traditional engineering disciplines. To improve wind turbines, it is required to predict how performance changes in response to multiple parametric design changes.</p> <p>The computational fluid dynamics (CFD) capability in Simcenter STAR-CCM+ offers an efficient and accurate set of fluid dynamics models and solvers with excellent parallel performance and scalability. It provides a solid foundation for multidisciplinary design exploration.</p> <p>Based upon advanced CFD calculation in Simcenter STAR-CCM+ one can to optimize e.g. the location of wind turbines in a windfarm or the shape of a blade in order to have a maximum harvesting of energy. Also e.g. the thermal behavior in the nacelle can optimized by CFD simulation.</p>
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5. Knowledge management and intellectual property

The innovation and IP management are key in the exploitation strategy of the project. In the framework of UPWARDS project, a specific team was created and dedicated to the innovation management. The innovation management team consist of the following persons: Jens Kjær Jørgensen, SINTEF, Innovation & IP manager, Jon Samseth, SINTEF, Coordinator contact, Andreas Wirsen, ITWM, Data manager, Alejandro Simon, Wavestone, Dissemination manager. This dedicated team monitors the progress of work in the WP's and its relevance for the final targeted innovation, takes necessary steps to source and select new ideas, communicates a good IP awareness practice to the partner, manage IP assessment and dissemination approvals, monitor developments and needs in market and at stakeholders etc.

Specific **deliverable D1.5 is dedicated to the Innovation Management Plan** and describes the framework, responsibilities, strategies and procedures applied in UPWARDS to assure that the consortium is working effectively and with the right focus towards to realising the planned innovations and exploitations.

5.1. Data management plan

UPWARDS Data Management Plan (for more details, see **Deliverable D1.4**) describes the initial strategy for data collection, storage, maintenance, and publication. This includes database architecture, data versioning, and metadata management.

As described in the UPWARDS GA, the data management plan considers the requirements for data integration and processing of UPWARDS virtual wind turbine. It includes information on how research data will be handled during and after the end of the project; what data will be collected, processed and/or generated; which methodology and standards will be applied; whether data will be shared/made open access and how data will be organized and accessible during and after the project.

The data collected by UPWARDS is technical data of new wind turbines required to parameterize integrated simulation model as well as social data. The data collected during the project will be classified into three specific categories: gold, green and white, and will be tracked and recorded in a project database.

UPWARDS will use the Zenodo depository (zenodo.org) to store all data which are released for free access. Zenodo is a free large capacity platform for the exchange and curation of research data managed by CERN established as a result of the OpenAIRE project.

5.2. IP management strategy

The IP management policy within UPWARDS project is covered by Innovation management team, more specifically Jens Kjær Jørgensen from SINTEF acts as IP manager. IP manager is responsible to communicate a good IP awareness practice to the consortium partners, manage IP assessment and dissemination approvals, follow up decisions on IP made by the General Assembly.

All results in UPWARDS should be conserved, and in many cases in addition, be disseminated or communicated in one or more ways. This concerns confidential deliverables, public deliverables, patenting, scientific dissemination (papers and conferences), communication activities to a broader audience, open access research data sharing, consortium internal storage of restricted final data including metadata.

Specific deadlines were agreed between partners for notification prior to any intended dissemination. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the publication. The objection is justified, if the protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background would be adversely affected,

the objecting Party's Legitimate Interests in relation to the Results or Background would be significantly harmed, the proposed publication includes Confidential Information of the objecting Party.

The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications. If an objection has been raised the involved Parties shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example by amendment to the planned publication and/or by protecting information before publication) and the objecting Party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate measures are taken following the discussion. The objecting Party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection. After 90 calendar days, the publication is permitted.

The protection of results that are decided to be excluded from publicity is the responsibility of the owner(s) of the results as described in the Grant Agreement

6. Standardization, policy-making and regulations

6.1. Identification of applicable standards

Standardization in the wind industry normally is related to tower structures and blade design, not to simulation models. However, the project results will surely have impact in the design of WT and wind farms i.e. TC obtaining timing, and thus standardization bodies will be involved in the project. We have identified the following certification organizations: IEC and CENELEC, and independent bodies such as DNV GL.

AWS will also play its part in the standardization activities as a company owned by a certification multinational, UL; *DNV GL is represented on the EEAB.*

7. Conclusions

Current report is the first version of the exploitation strategy plan at Month 24. The report will be updated as the project progresses, two main updates will be delivered at Month 36 (second version) and at Month 48 (final version).

The overall goal was to give an overview of an analysis of possible exploitation strategy of the project results.

The major added value of UPWARDS project is that it addresses at the same time several economic, technical, social and environmental aspects that will solve challenges is the design and optimization of large wind turbines. In this framework, a study done by the Wageningen University has identified potential stakeholders directly impacted by the project achievements. It contains a list of pre-identified stakeholders within the UPWARDS consortium, external stakeholders (within EU) including associations, private sector actors, members External Expert Advisory Board, and global networks.

Market study shows that the electricity production from renewable products is growing with an average rate of 2.7% per year; almost double the rate for the total electricity production (1.3%). Therefore, and accordingly to the SWOT analysis done in this report, the UPWARDS project has a good momentum in the market.

The development of larger and more efficient wind turbines will increase production of sustainable and renewable electricity in Europe and worldwide. The larger wind turbines are much more beneficial compared to the smaller wind turbines as they produce more energy more efficiently. In the last 2-3 decades the rated effect of wind turbines have risen from the kW range to the MW range. The natural next iteration is to design a 15 MW wind turbine. Therefore, one of the objectives in the UPWARDS project is to develop a 15MW virtual wind turbine. This has been designed by Siemens Gamesa (one of the project partners) together with SINTEF (the project coordinator).

Although UPWARDS' developments potentially have other sectors of application (e.g. aeronautics, aviation, automotive, to name some), the project's roadmap will focus on the wind energy sector, as the stage of development (TRL 4) is too early to be more specific.

In the long-term, UPWARDS integrated simulation framework will be introduced in the global market around the world that, as can be seen is currently led by China, USA, Germany and India. Globally, there is a worldwide growing trend in wind investments that UPWARDS will take advantage of once the developments are ready for commercialization.

The updated exploitation strategies by UPWARDS consortium partners at M24 were listed in the table 2.

Some key findings of innovation and IP management activities related to the exploitation strategy of the UPWARDS project were listed in the end of this report.